

OPTIMIZING FRESH PRODUCE DISTRIBUTION NETWORK IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *Uzbekistan region has emerged as a significant producer of fresh fruits and vegetables, catering to both domestic and international markets. This study aims to analyze the distribution network of fresh fruits and vegetables produced in Uzbekistan and identify optimal locations for Distribution Centers (DCs) using the AnyLogistix computational tool. The research focuses on a hypothetical company, "Uzbek Fresh," which is in its nascent stage and lacks historical demand data. By utilizing AnyLogistix, the demand for fresh fruits and vegetables in major Uzbekistan cities was estimated. Three distinct scenarios were developed for the distribution network using GreenField Analysis (GFA), incorporating customer locations, DC placement, and their respective demand volumes. The application of AnyLogistix aids in strategic planning for Uzbek Fresh, with the identified scenario offering alignment with the company's objectives and goals. This study contributes to enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the fresh produce distribution network in Uzbekistan, facilitating informed decision-making for industry stakeholders.*

Keywords: *supply chain management, simulation, distribution network, fresh fruit, vegetables, logistics, optimization, decision-making, AnyLogistix, strategic planning.*

1. Introduction

The global food industry has faced unprecedented challenges and disruptions in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, prompting profound reflections on food produce and distribution systems. Supply Chains (SCs) worldwide have been severely impacted, exposing long-standing vulnerabilities, inefficiencies, and volatility within the industry [1]. The pandemic-induced disruptions have led to shortages, supply chain fragmentation, significant losses, and even bankruptcies among food companies [2].

Amidst the crisis, the demand for food surged as people stocked up on supplies due to fear of prolonged isolation and potential food shortages [2,3]. This surge in demand presented both challenges and opportunities for the food industry globally. In Germany, for instance, food retailing faced significant challenges but also capitalized on emerging opportunities for growth [3]. Despite the difficulties, the food sector had to continue produce and distribution to ensure the population's survival during the pandemic.

In Uzbekistan, the impact of the pandemic on the food industry echoed the global trends. While the international market for Uzbek produce was affected by COVID-19 restrictions, domestic produce and consumption remained relatively stable. The country continued its agricultural exports, albeit facing logistical challenges and fluctuations in demand. The post-pandemic situation in Uzbekistan and globally remains uncertain, with ongoing fluctuations in demand and supply chain dynamics.

The fruit and vegetable sector in Uzbekistan has shown resilience amidst these challenges. Despite disruptions, Uzbekistan continued to produce and export fresh fruits and vegetables, contributing to its agricultural economy. However, the unstable global situation underscores the

need for a robust and adaptive distribution network to ensure the efficient flow of fresh produce within Uzbekistan and beyond.

Given the uncertainties and opportunities in the market, the utilization of computational tools for Supply Chain Management (SCM) in the agri-food industry becomes imperative. These tools offer opportunities to analyze logistics problems, enhance supply chain efficiency, and improve product quality and food safety [4,5,6]. AnyLogistix software, in particular, has emerged as a valuable tool for simulating supply chains and optimizing logistics solutions [6,7,8,]

Against this backdrop, this article aims to analyze the distribution network for fresh fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan, particularly in the post-pandemic context, and identify optimal locations for Distribution Centers (DCs) using simulation techniques with AnyLogistix software. This research is crucial for enhancing the resilience and efficiency of Uzbekistan's fresh produce distribution network, ensuring the reliable supply of agricultural products to domestic and international markets.

The structure of this article is as follows: Section 2 provides a theoretical foundation on logistics and supply chain management, introduces the AnyLogistix software, and reviews relevant literature. Section 3 outlines the characteristics of the problem and the specific supply chain under study. Section 4 presents the application of AnyLogistix in optimizing the distribution network for fresh fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan, accompanied by an analysis of the results. Finally, Section 5 concludes with the authors' reflections and considerations.

2. Content

The background section offers a thorough explanation of logistics and supply chain management (SCM) principles, emphasizing their importance in efficiently overseeing the movement of goods, services, and information from origin to consumption. Logistics, as defined by the Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP), involves the planning and control of these flows to meet customer needs effectively.

Supply chains are described as interconnected networks of entities collaborating to deliver products to customers. SCM entails integrating processes, departments, and companies to optimize material, information, and financial flows along the value chain. Strategic decisions such as facility location and distribution network structure are key components of SCM, underscoring the significance of coordinated management across the supply chain.

Efficient SCM is critical in the agri-food sector due to product perishability, the necessity for timely transportation, and the imperative of maintaining quality and food safety standards. Despite its importance, there is a noted scarcity of research specifically focused on the agri-food supply chain, indicating room for further exploration and enhancement in this area.

In summary, this background section lays a solid groundwork for comprehending the fundamental concepts and challenges within logistics and SCM, setting the context for the subsequent analysis of the distribution network for fresh fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan.

3.1 AnyLogistix® Software

The AnyLogistix® software, developed by Anylogic®, provides an advanced solution tailored for supply chain design. It addresses various decision-making challenges within real-world logistics systems through its optimization and simulation capabilities [8]. AnyLogistix offers an accessible platform for researchers, students, and professionals to model supply chains, conduct experiments, and analyze results.

With minimal parameterization requirements, AnyLogistix is user-friendly and suitable for individuals with limited programming experience. It enables users to explore multiple scenarios and experiments within a single project, facilitating comprehensive analysis. The software generates dedicated databases to store project information, ensuring data integrity and accessibility [8].

An essential feature of AnyLogistix is its ability to identify optimal Distribution Center (DC) locations using GreenField Analysis (GFA), also known as Center-Of-Gravity Analysis. GFA aims to pinpoint suitable locations for new DCs based on factors such as customer locations, distances to customers, and customer demands. By calculating the weighted distances of customers to potential warehouse sites, GFA helps identify regions that minimize distribution costs [8,9,10,11].

The application of computational tools like AnyLogistix has gained traction in decision-making processes across various industries. Recent literature highlights the software's versatility, with a significant focus on addressing challenges related to vaccination distribution and the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, [8] investigated the pandemic's impact on food retail supply chains in Germany using AnyLogistix. Similarly, [2,4,8] utilized the software to simulate scenarios of disruptions in the food supply chain of a north Indian state's Public Distribution System (PDS).

These studies underscore the utility of AnyLogistix in tackling complex logistical challenges, making it a valuable tool for addressing issues within the agri-food industry supply chain. The software's ability to simulate and optimize distribution networks aligns well with the objectives of this article, emphasizing its relevance in addressing logistical complexities and enhancing supply chain resilience.

3. Structuring the Problem

The agricultural sector plays a crucial role in Uzbekistan's economy, with the country being known for its production of various fruits and vegetables. While cultivation is widespread across the nation, regions like Ferghana Valley, Surkhandarya, and Bukhara stand out for their production of fresh fruits and vegetables. Unlike some areas focusing on specific crops for processing or export, these regions primarily grow produce for direct consumption.

The domestic market for fresh fruits and vegetables has seen steady growth in Uzbekistan, with favorable climatic conditions and fertile soil supporting year-round cultivation. This allows for multiple harvests throughout the year, ensuring a continuous supply of fresh produce to meet consumer demand.

The increase in production, particularly of seedless varieties and premium-quality fruits and vegetables, has strengthened Uzbekistan's ability to meet domestic demand and reduce reliance on imports, enhancing its competitiveness in both local and international markets.

The largest share of the total volume of fresh fruits and vegetables products is 14.4% in Surkhandarya region. It was also noted that the largest indicators fell on the regions of Jizzakh (12.4%), Syrdarya (11.2%), Bukhara (8.4%) and Andijan (8.0%). The smallest indicators of fresh fruits and vegetables products were observed in Tashkent (2.8%) and Namangan (4.4%) regions. In 2020, high growth rates were recorded in Fergana (110.2%), Namangan (109.5%), Republic of Karakalpakstan (107.5%), Bukhara (104.6%) and Surkhandarya (104.2 %) regions.

Uzbek Fresh operates within major producing regions of Uzbekistan, strategically located near key production centers such as Andijan, Namangan, and Samarkand. The company aims to

become a leading distributor of fresh fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan and capture a significant share of the domestic market by 2025.

Fig.1 The volume of cultivation of fresh fruits and vegetables products in the cross section of regions.

The company's clientele includes retailers, wholesalers, and local markets, necessitating strategically positioned DCs to ensure timely delivery and meet customer demands. Given the perishable nature of fruits and vegetables, daily deliveries are crucial, requiring close proximity to customers. Uzbek Fresh utilizes refrigerated vehicles, both owned and outsourced, for transportation, ensuring product freshness and quality during transit.

As a newcomer to the market, Uzbek Fresh faces challenges in understanding consumer preferences, estimating demand, and identifying optimal sales locations to position DCs across Uzbekistan. Agility in supply chain operations is essential to ensure prompt delivery of fresh products to customers, minimizing losses and maintaining customer satisfaction.

Lacking historical sales data, Uzbek Fresh encounters difficulties in demand forecasting. Understanding the Uzbek consumer profile and consumption patterns is crucial for predicting demand and effectively managing supply chain operations. Analyzing consumer behavior across different regions of Uzbekistan will provide valuable insights for strategic decision-making.

Overall, the growth of the agricultural sector and Uzbekistan's position as a key producer of fresh fruits and vegetables present opportunities for companies like Uzbek Fresh to establish efficient distribution networks and capitalize on the growing domestic demand for fresh produce.

4. Results

To address the distribution challenges in Uzbekistan's fresh fruit and vegetable market, we employed the AnyLogistix software. Our objective was to estimate demand and determine optimal customer locations, focusing on the analysis of the most populous cities in Uzbekistan. Utilizing the GreenField Analysis (GFA) feature, we aimed to identify suitable locations for Distribution Centers (DCs) to streamline supply chain operations.

We utilized specific options within AnyLogistix, including "Add scenario date" and "One customer per location with demand proportional to population density". These features enabled us to distribute demand based on the population density of Uzbekistan's major cities. This approach is particularly useful when historical data is limited, allowing us to create relevant data for analysis purposes. Orders were set to occur daily to reflect the consistent demand for fresh produce.

In the initial stage, demand estimation was based on the average per capita consumption of fresh fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan. This figure was then adjusted to account for the desired market penetration rate set by our hypothetical company, "Uzbek Fresh," divided by the total number of days in a year. The resulting value represented the daily demand in kilograms of fresh produce per individual consumer.

For example, a population of 1 million people would consume an average of a certain number of fresh fruits and vegetables per day. Utilizing this foundational information, AnyLogistix was executed to conduct the analysis. The software provided insights into optimal DC locations and helped visualize the distribution of demand across the country's major cities, facilitating strategic decision-making in supply chain management for fresh produce in Uzbekistan.

Figure 2. Initial setup in AnyLogistix for demand forecasting.

In the subsequent phase of our analysis, we employed AnyLogistix's estimations for each city in Uzbekistan to refine our data and harmonize it with regional consumption trends. By referencing consumption behaviors across diverse regions of the country, we fine-tuned the calculated demand accordingly. We delineated consumption percentages for key regions in Uzbekistan based on our investigation. Tashkent Region: 46.4%, Ferghana Region: 25%, Surkhandarya Region: 19%, Bukhara Region: 5%, Khorezm Region: 4%. Utilizing Excel, we processed the initial demand data from AnyLogistix, ensuring that the aggregate demand for each region, encompassing Uzbekistan's 100 largest cities, concurred with these consumption percentages.

Once the adjustments were made, the modified file was brought back into AnyLogistix, and a fresh scenario was set up to incorporate the revised demand information. Transitioning to the subsequent phase, our attention turned to configuring the GreenField Analysis (GFA) module. Under the "GFA experiment" feature, we ran simulations for three different scenarios to assess them in line with the company's principles, objectives, and limitations:

- C1 - 2 distribution centers and no level of customer service
- C2 - 150 km for the level of customer service.
- C3 - 100 km for the level of customer service.

The results depicting the distribution network of fresh fruits and vegetables across Uzbekistan for each of the three scenarios are displayed in Figures 3, 4, and 5. Furthermore, Table 1 offers a detailed breakdown of AnyLogistix's findings for each scenario. In the visuals, blue markers denote customer locations, red markers represent Distribution Centers (DCs), and the brown marker indicates the location of the company operating in Uzbekistan.

Figure 3. Distribution network of scenario C1.

Figure 4. Distribution network of scenario C2.

Figure 5. Distribution network of scenario C3.

The GFA application identified the most suitable DC locations for each scenario. In scenario C1, the distribution network is served by only two DCs, resulting in DC 1, located near Uzbekistan's capital, Tashkent, bearing the burden. DC 1 is responsible for catering to 76 customers across Ferghana and Surkhandarya regions, with an annual demand of 7,187,383 kilograms of fresh fruits and vegetables. This scenario emphasizes an optimal location strategy based on the specific demands of customers.

In scenario C3, the customer service radius is reduced to 100 kilometers to optimize the distribution of DCs with lower demand. Consequently, eight DCs are established, each catering to a specific region of Uzbekistan. Notably, to better serve Surkhandarya, Bukhara, and Kashqadarya regions. DC 7 strategically serves Khorezm region, conveniently located near the emerging centers of Urganch and Nukus in western Uzbekistan.

Meanwhile, DC 2 efficiently covers Tashkent region, servicing all 25 customers located in the Northeast. This scenario adopts a strategy centered on service level, considering demand and proximity of customers to the DCs.

Table 1. Number of fresh fruit and vegetable distribution center for Republic of Uzbekistan.

	DC's	Number of Customer	Demand (kg)	Distance (km)
Result C1	DC 1	76	7,187,383	474
	DC 2	19	1,303,323	388
	Total	100	8,490,706	862
Result C2	DC 1	12	832,312	150
	DC 2	9	490,250	129
	DC 3	21	1,579,665	150
	DC 4	28	3,551,954	150
	DC 5	25	2,036,525	107
	Total	100	8,490,706	686
Result C3	DC 1	5	309,891	100
	DC 2	25	2,036,525	100
	DC 3	11	828,973	100
	DC 4	14	931,051	100
	DC 5	8	429,459	45
	DC 6	4	402,853	90
	DC 7	9	472,919	81
	DC 8	9	3,079,035	83
	Total	100	8,490,706	799

5. Conclusions

The AnyLogistix software has proven to be both robust and user-friendly as a computational tool for aiding decision-making in supply chain management (SCM). Its versatility extends to supporting more intricate analyses. Apart from guiding strategic decision-making, especially in instances where historical data on regional demand is absent, AnyLogistix facilitates the creation and simulation of various distribution network scenarios and potential DC placement locations.

Considering the strategic aim of reaching all regions of Uzbekistan with exceptional service quality, aligning with the goal of becoming a leading producer and distributor of fresh fruits and vegetables, especially given the unique aspects of the produce trade, scenario C2 emerges as a favorable option. It is well-suited to the organization's strategic objectives

This research can provide a foundation for companies operating in the fresh fruit and vegetable sector, as well as other industries, to analyze and enhance their supply chain management practices and production outcomes through simulation techniques.

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